

Does Special Relativity Follow from Wave Nature?

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Historically two types of “free” mechanical motions were considered, that of Newtonian mechanics $x=vt$ ($v=\text{constant}$) and classical waves such as waves on a string which were described in terms of Newton’s laws for a continuous medium. It seems these two were considered as fundamentally different phenomena. Equations of motion were developed for classical mechanics as well as electromagnetic phenomena. Maxwell discovered that electromagnetic equations allowed for a classical wavelike solution which he identified as light. In the early 1900s it was realized that to retain electromagnetic equations invariance as seen from a constant moving frame moving, Lorentz transformations were needed. In 1905 Einstein obtained these transformations in a different manner considering that light has the same vacuum speed when viewed from different constant moving frames. Later in the 1920s quantum mechanics was developed using the idea of a probability wave $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ for a free particle beginning with the work of deBroglie who made use of ideas of special relativity.

In this note we suggest that there seems to be one fundamental “free” mechanical motion, namely that associated with a wave $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ whether one considers a classical wave or a quantum free particle. Classical mechanics is a mapping into a continuous $x-t$ space, we argue, and describes energy and momentum motion in this continuous space. This same description also occurs for classical waves. The medium undergoes a somewhat complicated nonlocal change, but the “velocity” of the wave maps to a continuous local space time i.e. $v=x/t=dx/dt$ where $E= pv$. $E=pv$, however, is only a description of energy momentum propagation given in a simple form. It does not describe the overall picture. We argue the same is true for the simple $x=vt$ ($v=\text{constant}$). It seems that an overall wave structure is associated with energy and momentum and for free motion this is linked with $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. If this wave is fundamental one may argue that its phase may remain constant when viewed from different frames moving at constant v . Special relativity would then follow from this requirement and so is in a sense a consequence of wave behaviour. We investigate these ideas.

Classical Action

A full description of classical mechanics began with Newton’s laws. Later Lagrangian (action) and Hamiltonian formalisms were developed to describe the same motion. These approaches consider a particle as represented by a point $x(t)$. Changes such as acceleration or even velocity are defined by small intervals dx and dt . For example, dx may be constant and dt different in each dx if a particle accelerates. Thus on the one hand one has continuous space time $x(t)$, but on the other “pieces” of space time dx and dt . The idea is that dx and dt are supposed to approach zero, but they do so at different rates and so it seems that a view of small intervals with different sizes is a more accurate picture. Thus the continuous form $x(t)$ i.e. $x=vt$ for v constant seems to be a kind of averaging or approximation used to describe energy -momentum flow. This may have relevance because there is a second classical phenomenon involving energy-momentum-namely classical wave motion.

Historically even though this motion may be described using Newtonian mechanics as in the analysis of a wave on a string, it was treated as a separate phenomenon associated with a medium. A “free” particle on the other hand may move through a vacuum. In both cases, however, one has “free” motion associated with an energy-momentum relationship i.e. $E=pv$ for a classical wave and $p=Ev$ for a free particle (special relativistic form). In the nonrelativistic case $p=Ev$ becomes $p=m_0 v$. In other words there is a similarity between the energy-momentum relationships, but the actual motions are very different or at least this was the case before quantum mechanics.

With quantum mechanics, de Broglie considered a “free” quantum particle to also be associated with wavelike motion. The problem which arose, however, is that there is no medium so Born associated this wave motion with a probability wave. Nevertheless we argue that wavelike-like motion may be the fundamental form of energy-momentum free motion. Thus the motion of a free particle and a classical wave are both linked to this wavelike approach, yet have different energy-momentum relationships. The question is to find a formalism which accounts for both. Such a formalism seems to be associated with the classical action for a free particle which is part of Lagrange’s theory i.e. $\text{Action} = \int L(v,x,t) dt$.

A classical wave has an energy momentum relationship of $E=pv$, but a wave equation $\frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} W(x,t) = \frac{1}{v} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} W(x,t)$ ((1)) is needed to describe the motion through the medium. This leads to a solution of $C_1 \cos(-Et+px)$ ((2)). This relationship contains the energy-momentum one if one sets $-E dt + p dx = 0$. ((3))

Thus the form $-Et+px$ is key to describing a classical wave, yet it is associated with a differential equation ((1)) which describes physical properties of space time if a classical wave passes through a medium. One may notice that:

$$\frac{d}{dx} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} W(x,t) = -pp W(x,t) \text{ and } \frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} W(x,t) = EE W(x,t) \quad ((4))$$

Thus the wave differential equation is not only associated with $-Et+px$, but with two differential eigenvalue equations. One may note that x and t are treated as independent when taking partial derivatives, but $v=dx/dt$ i.e. $x(t)$. The second derivative is required to retrieve $\cos(-Et+px)$.

Mathematically, if one considers $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ which is an extension of $\cos(-Et+px)$ one may form an eigenvalue differential equation with only one derivative, but a complex “i” appears:

$$-i \frac{d}{dx} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \exp(-iEt+ipx) = p \exp(-iEt+ipx) \quad \text{and} \quad i \frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \exp(-iEt+ipx) = E \exp(-iEt+ipx) \quad ((5))$$

By taking a second derivative one may obtain the classical wave equation so ((4)) and ((5)) are closely linked to the same form $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. The question becomes: Is there a physical representation for ((5))? As a first step, one may notice that $-Et+px$ leads to:

$$\frac{d}{dx} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} (-Et+px) = p \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (-Et+px) = E \quad ((6))$$

This is in fact the basis for forming ((5)). $-Et+px$ which treats t and x as independent is of the same form as the classical free particle action, both in a relativistic and nonrelativistic form i.e.

A relativistic = $-m_0 t \sqrt{1-v^2} = -Et+px$ where $E=m_0/\sqrt{1-v^2}$ and $p=Ev$ and

A nonrelativistic = $.5m_0 t v^2 = -Et+px$ ((7)) where $E=pp/2m$ and $p=m_0 v$

The classical action is used to obtain the equation of motion of a classical particle, but we argue that it is really finding energy-momentum flow mapped to a continuous x-t space. Actual motion, like in the classical wave approach, is more complicated and involves differential eigenvalue equations.

As a result, $-Et+px$ is not only a fundamental part of a classical wave, it is the classical action of a free particle. In addition, $-Et+px$ is part of the “wave” obtained from electromagnetic equations by Maxwell i.e. the electric field behaves as $\cos(-Et+px)$ etc. Thus the form $-Et+px$ is fundamental to classical mechanical free particle motion, classical waves like water or string waves and light.

This question: Is there a physical representation of ((5))? still remains. This we argue is an important issue because it would suggest wave nature as the fundamental mechanism behind energy-momentum motion. For a free particle we argued that Newtonian mechanics considers tiny regions dx and dt. We have argued in previous notes that $\exp(ipx) = \cos(px) + i \sin(px)$ represents two spatially shifted probability-like distributions defining a resolution-wave with wavelength p. The two shifted distributions have a modulus of 1 showing that a free particle’s energy-momentum maps into continuous motion in x-t although “behind the scenes” there is actually resolution and wave motion which manifests itself physically through interference.

Special Relativity

As a result of the above sections, we argue that an intrinsic wave-like motion is associated with energy-momentum motion whether it be a classical wave or quantum particle. Newtonian mechanics describes a continuous motion in all x and t i.e. a mapping of this wave which removes the resolution and in the classical world wavelengths are too tiny to be readily observed although there are experiments which report measurements of tiny quantum fluctuations in objects as large as about 70 kg.

If this is the case, we argue that perhaps special relativity is also a consequence of wave-like motion. We have seen that wavelike motion is linked to differential equations which are ultimately linked to $-Et+px$ for a free particle or classical wave. If this is considered to be a dot product of (p,E) and (x,t) with a particular metric then it would be an invariant. In other words the phase of a free wave $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ would be an essential physical property which remains unchanged if viewed from a frame moving at constant velocity. From this one may obtain the Lorentz transformation form if one insists that m_0 at rest at $x=0$ at t_0 has $x'/t'=v$ as seen by a moving frame (at constant v). Thus we argue that wave phase invariance as viewed in different frames moving with constant velocities may be the driver of the results of special relativity.

Conclusion

In conclusion, even though classical wave behaviour (wave on a string) may be formulated in terms of Newtonian mechanics, we argue that the fundamental underlying behaviour of

energy-momentum motion may be wavelike. This holds not only for a classical wave, but for a free particle. $-Et+px$ not only appears in a classical wave and light wave from Maxwell's electromagnetic equations, but is equivalent to both the relativistic and nonrelativistic classical actions if x and t are treated as independent. We argue that there exist relations $p=Ev$ for a particle and $E=pv$ for a classical wave or zero mass wave, but that there is associated motion linked to waves and resolution. In particular one may use $-Et+px$ to develop a differential eigenvalue equation which describes this kind of motion i.e. $-i\partial/\partial x \text{ partial exp}(-iEt+ipx) = p \text{ exp}(-iEt+ipx)$ and $i\partial/\partial t \text{ partial exp}(-iEt+ipx) = E \text{ exp}(-iEt+ipx)$. This is a complex equation i.e. it represents two dimensions, but may be thought of as two sets of shifted probability densities which map to 1. In particular $\cos(px)$ represents one resolution scheme in space and $\sin(px)$ is a shifted one showing how motion occurs. The modulus is 1 to map into a continuous $x-t$ space linked with $v=x/t$, but really nonlocal behaviour exists as is seen from two slit experiments etc. Newtonian mechanics we argue is a mapping of the resolution-wave picture to a continuous $x-t$ one.

If wave like motion is the underlying behaviour of energy-momentum motion, one may postulate that the phase $-Et+px$ of $\text{exp}(-iEt+ipx)$ may be an invariant as seen from frames moving at constant velocities. If that is the case, one may derive the form of a Lorentz transformation based on this idea alone. In other words special relativity would follow from wave-like motion.